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THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INCOME TAX IN MODERN TAX SYSTEM.

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Abstract: Tax system is so important for the government economic process, and in modern countries know that tax is a heart of the economics. As we know that this system is related to such kind of taxes such as income tax, sales tax, property tax and others. In this article we will discuss income tax in financial system of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: tax, financial system, tax payer, income, resident, non-resident.

Introducing

An **income tax** is a tax imposed on individuals or entities (taxpayers) in respect of the income or profits earned by them (commonly called taxable income). Income tax generally is computed as the product of a tax rate times the taxable income. Taxation rates may vary by type or characteristics of the taxpayer and the type of income.

The tax rate may increase as taxable income increases (referred to as graduated or progressive tax rates). The tax imposed on companies is usually known as corporate tax and is commonly levied at a flat rate. Individual income is often taxed at progressive rates where the tax rate applied to each additional unit of income increases (e.g., the first \$10,000 of income taxed at 0%, the next \$10,000 taxed at 1%, etc.). Most jurisdictions exempt local charitable organizations from tax. Income from investments may be taxed at different (generally lower) rates than other types of income. Credits of various sorts may be allowed that reduce tax. Some jurisdictions impose the higher of an income tax or a tax on an alternative base or measure of income.

Taxable income of taxpayers' resident in the jurisdiction is generally total income less income producing expenses and other deductions. Generally, only net gain from the sale of property, including goods held for sale, is included in income. The income of a corporation's shareholders usually includes distributions of profits from the corporation. Deductions typically include all income-producing or business expenses including an allowance for recovery of costs of business assets. Many jurisdictions allow notional deductions for individuals and may allow deduction of some personal expenses. Most jurisdictions either do not tax income earned outside the jurisdiction or allow a credit for taxes paid to other jurisdictions on such income.

Nonresidents are taxed only on certain types of income from sources within the jurisdictions, with few exceptions.

Most jurisdictions require self-assessment of the tax and require payers of some types of income to withhold tax from those payments. Advance payments of tax by taxpayers may be required. Taxpayers not timely paying tax owed are generally subject to significant penalties, which may include jail for individuals. Taxable income of taxpayers' resident in the jurisdiction is generally total income less income producing expenses and other deductions. Generally, only net gain from the sale of property, including goods held for sale, is included in income. The income of a corporation's shareholders usually includes distributions of profits from the corporation. Deductions typically include all income-producing or business expenses including an allowance for recovery of costs of business assets. Many jurisdictions allow notional deductions for individuals and may allow deduction of some personal expenses.

As the old adage goes, only two things in life are certain: death and taxes. Taxes can be a financial burden, but paying taxes is important for several reasons. Taxes are used to fund all manner of publicly-funded services including the military, public education, infrastructure such as roads and parks, police and fire departments, and public retirement and health programs such as Social Security and Medicare in the United States. Simply put, taxes provide the funds that a country needs to survive.

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[No two national tax systems are alike](#)

Taxes come in many forms, including sales tax, income tax, property tax, inheritance and estate taxes, excise tax, and more. Plus, tax rates and regulations vary greatly from country to country, and even within different parts of the same country. For example, most U.S. states charge some form of income tax, but an individual state's income tax rate may be anywhere from 1% to 13.3%. Moreover, seven states (Alaska, Florida, Nevada, South Dakota, Texas, Washington, and Wyoming) do not collect any state income tax at all, and two more (New Hampshire and Tennessee) tax interest and dividend income, but not wages or salaries.

Similarly, most U.S. states charge a state sales tax, but some do not. However, states without a sales tax or an income tax may add or raise other taxes to make up for the deficit, such as implementing higher property tax rates. Finally, most

governments that levy taxes charge different percentages based upon the amount of income or type of goods being taxed. For example, a person who makes \$40k a year may pay 12% in income taxes while their next-door neighbor, who makes \$200k, pays 25% or more. Similarly, sales of basic needs such as groceries are typically taxed at a much lower rate than sales of luxury items such as tobacco products or a new car. For this article, we'll compare three main types of taxes: personal income tax, corporate tax, and sales tax.

Top 10 Countries with the Highest Personal Income Tax Rates - Trading Economics 2021:

- Japan - 55.97%
- Denmark - 55.90%
- Austria - 55.00%
- Sweden - 52.90%
- Aruba - 52.00%
- Belgium - 50.00% (tie)
- Israel - 50.00% (tie)
- Slovenia - 50.00% (tie)

Top 10 Countries with the Highest Personal Income Tax Rates - Trading Economics 2022:

1. IvoryCoast - 60%
2. Finland - 56.95%
3. Japan - 55.97%
4. Denmark - 55.90%
5. Austria - 55.00%
6. Sweden - 52.90%
7. Aruba - 52.00%
8. Belgium - 50.00% (tie)
9. Israel - 50.00% (tie)
10. Slovenia - 50.00% (tie)

As we see that in these countries are one of the grands of the world, their tax system is so systematic and especially income tax is so high than other countries, and the rate of tax is also high to revenues.

Let's discuss with our tax rate:

On 26 July 2022 the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan (the "RUz") No. 785 "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the RUz in connection with the improvement of tax and customs legislation" was adopted and entered into force on 27 July 2022. Some individual provisions of the Law have different terms of entry into force.

Some of the novelties provided by this Law were already announced earlier in 2022 by the relevant Presidential Decrees and after the adoption of the Law the changes were duly incorporated in the Uzbek legislation.

In this review, we have summarized what are, in our opinion, the most significant changes. However, for the full information on changes, we recommend also consulting the text of the relevant legislative acts, as well as the current Uzbek Tax Code (the "TC RUz") and the Uzbek Customs Code.

Personal income tax (PIT) and corporate income tax (CIT) benefits for holders of securities and bonds

□ Starting from 1 April 2022 to 31 December 2024 a number of tax benefits are being implemented for securities holders:

On 26 July 2022 the Law #ZRU-785 was adopted stipulating changes to the Uzbek tax and customs legislation.

Overview of changes in the tax and customs legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

□ For individuals - both residents and non-residents of the RUz - dividend income on shares is exempt from personal income tax (PIT) (previously, for resident individuals the dividend income

on shares was subject to a 5% tax, while for non-resident individuals the dividend income on

shares was subject to a 10% tax).

□ For legal entities that are non-residents of the RUz - dividend income on shares is subject to a 5% corporate income tax (CIT) similarly to legal entities that are residents of the RUz (previously, for legal entities that are non-residents of the RUz the dividend income on shares was subject to a 10% tax).

□ For individuals and legal entities – both residents and non-residents of the RUz – accrued interest income on bonds of enterprises is exempt from PIT and CIT (previously, for resident individuals the income was subject to a 5% tax, and for non-resident individuals it was subject to a 10% tax, while for resident legal entities it was subject to a 15% tax, and for non-resident legal entities without a permanent establishment in the RUz it was subject to a 10% tax).

▶ Starting from 1 May 2022 the PIT rate on income received by non-resident individuals under employment and civil contracts is set at 12% (previously 20%).

Value added tax (VAT)

▶ For the period starting from 1 April 2022 to 1 January 2025, the import of spare parts of medical equipment and products, as well as consumables for medical purposes, in the territory of the RUz is exempt from VAT.

Excise tax

▶ Starting from 1 January 2022 the excise tax for mobile communication services provided by mobile operators is set at 10% (previously 15%).

Property tax for legal entities

▶ Starting from 1 January 2022 while determining the tax base for property tax for legal entities in relation to real estate objects, which cost is lower than the minimum cost set by the TC RUz for 1 sq.m. of an object situated in a certain location, the taxpayer has the right to consider the results of an independent valuation conducted within previous two years. Real estate objects that are not covered by the minimum cost are determined by the legislation.

▶ Starting from 1 April 2022 antenna-mast metal structures located in rural areas (excluding cities and regional centers)), including structures installed on them and being an integral part are exempt from property tax.

Land tax for legal entities

▶ Starting from 1 April 2022 land plots, occupied by antenna-mast metal structures (including structures installed on them and being an integral part), located in rural areas (excluding cities and regional centers, are exempt from land tax.

▶ Starting from 1 January 2023 to 1 January 2026, taxpayers who have modern automated complexes for slaughtering livestock, as well as taxpayers who process and produce finished leather products, are exempt from land tax.

Social tax

▶ Starting from 1 April 2022 to 1 January 2025, social tax is levied at the rate of 1% for those manufacturers whose total income for a relevant reporting period amounted to:

- ▶ At least 60% of sales proceeds from children's, women's and sports shoes, artificial (eco) leather, accessories, shoe forms and soles;
- ▶ At least 80% from export of footwear, leather goods and fur products.

CHANGES IN THE CUSTOMS LEGISLATION

▶ Tariff benefits in the form of exemption from customs duty are not applied to goods purchased at the expense of funds (loans, credits) of international financial institutions and foreign government financial organizations, refinanced or re-credited through the Uzbek commercial banks.

▶ The applied privileges related to the customs duties adopted before 1 July 2022 by the acts of the President and the Cabinet of Ministers of the RUZ are valid until their expiration date.

Conclusion

Income from salary includes wages, pension, annuity, gratuity, fees, commission, profits, leave encashment, annual accretion and transferred balance in recognized Provident Fund (PF) and contribution to employees' pension account.

Rental Income from properties owned by a person other than those which are occupied by him are charged as income from house property. If property is vacant then a notional income is included under this head.

Income from business or profession includes profit/loss from a business entity or a profession, any interest, salary or bonus to a partner of a firm.

Income from capital gains includes long term capital gains (LTCG) and short-term capital gains (STCG) on sale of any capital assets.

Income from other sources includes interest on bank deposits and securities, dividend, royalty income, winning on lotteries and races and gifts received among others.

In my opinion, there are some problems in our tax system, because it is not the same for everyone. Firstly, income tax rate is lower than other countries and this is a chance to our businessmen and population, however, I think that it is difficult for medium workers. In Uzbekistan myriad workers get overall 1 million soums and they have to pay 120 thousand soums to tax worker's revenue is only 880 thousand soums. That is not enough for the family and also in our modern world there are some jobs like

logistics, traders. Their overall revenue is minimum 300 dollars and I do not understand that why they do not pay tax for their revenues. It is not equation.

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